

Breeding methods — hybrid rice

Combining ability and heterosis of agronomic traits in indica PGMS lines and their hybrids

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In a two-line hybrid rice system, photo-period-sensitive, genic male sterile (PGMS) rices are used. Knowledge of the combining ability and heterosis of PGMS lines and their hybrids is needed for selecting good combiners for high vigor combinations.

We crossed indica PGMS lines W6154S, W6184S, W6417S, W7415S, and W6434S, and 6 test lines in a 5 × 6 mating pattern. Thirty F₁ hybrids, 6 testers, and 2 check combinations were planted at 25 × 17 cm, in a random design with three replications.

General combining ability (GCA) and specific combining ability (SCA) were analyzed for grain yield per plant and 10 other agronomic traits. GCA and SCA were significant for all traits, indicating that additive and nonadditive interactions were important (Table 1).

Variations due to SCA were greater than those due to GCA for grain yield per plant and fertile spikelets per panicle,

suggesting dominant gene action.

Variations due to GCA were greater than those due to SCA for other traits.

PGMS lines W6154S and W6184S were good general combiners for grain yield per plant (Table 2). Heterobeltiosis ranged from 246.8 to 2.0% for grain yield per plant. Combinations W6154S/Teqing 2 and W6184S/02428 yielded 3.2 and 12.8% more, respectively, than check Shan-you 63, the best three-line system combination. ■

Table 2. Estimates of SCA and GCA effects for yield per plant of PGMS lines and cross combinations.

Female parent	SCA of crosses with each given male parent						GCA ^{ab}	Variance of SCA
	Minghui 63	Teqing 2	02428	Qingsiai	Ce 64	Ce 49		
W6154S	0.659	6.759	7.384	-3.691	-03.744	-7.368	5.561*a	22.887
W6184S	0.591	1.714	13.626	-3.653	-6.399	-5.880	5.402*a	48.322
WG417S	-7.227	-2.520	-4.125	7.296	2.980	3.596	-2.007 b	29.216
W7415S	1.432	5.972	-14.364	-1.922	5.138	3.744	-3.328 b	50.389
W6434S	4.554	-11.926	-2.521	1.970	2.024	5.907	-5.628*b	35.180
GCA ^b	2.761	2.354	0.276	-1.465	-1.572	-2.355		
	a	ab	ab	b	b	c		
Variance of SCA	14.403	16.043	50.673	30.133	11.386	109.927	K ² _{fm} = 46.51	

^a* = Significantly different from zero at 5% level of probability. ^bDifferent letters show significant difference in GCA at 5% level of probability.

Table 1. Analysis of variance for combining ability for yield and yield components of PGMS lines.

Source ^b	MS and F test for agronomic characters										
	Yield/plant	Panicles/plant	Spikelets/panicle	Fertility (%)	Grains/panicle	1000-grain weight	Days to heading	Plant height	Tillering ability	Panicle length	Spikelet density
GCA1	481.0**	7.5*	1091.3**	1118.4**	3110.8**	71.7**	230.1**	31.7**	45.2	1.2	152.2**
GCA2	70.2*	26.8**	43172.3**	1813.6**	3377.2**	201.0**	1467.3**	1339.7**	60.6**	43.7**	5576.5**
SCA	166.7**	2.8	944.0**	315.8**	1955.7**	2.6**	74.8**	65.5**	5.9	2.7**	113.1**
VGCAIVSCA	0.24	12.4	9.95	1.46	0.26	6.71	4.17	4.08	18.44	3.67	11.48

^a*** = significant at the 5% and 1% level of probability, respectively. ^bGCA1 = general combining ability (GCA) of female parents; GCA2 = GCA of male parents. VGCA and VSCA = variance due to GCA and SCA.

CIS28-10S, a new indica photoperiod-sensitive, genic male-sterile rice

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CIS28, a B₉F₄ progeny of the cross Caloro/IR28, was bred by Yuan Longping in 1985 as a cyto-nucleoplasm hybrid. We found a spontaneous mutant in 1986, and the indica, photoperiod-sensitive, genic male-sterile germplasm CIS28-10S, one of the derivatives isolated from the spontaneous mutant,

was released in 1989 for use in developing two-line hybrids.

We evaluated CIS28-10S at Xiangtan (28° N) in 1990. Fifty individual plants were spaced at 15 × 20 cm. Plant height, days to 50% flowering, panicle length, grains per panicle, 1,000-grain weight, exerted stigma rate, sterility-transformation and fertility-transformation stages were measured, with CIS28 as the check (see table).

CIS28-10S has very strong ratooning ability, high-yielding agronomic characters, and good grain quality. Floral characters that influence outcrossing rates are also very good.

Performance of CIS28-10S in Xiangtan, China, 1990.

Parameter	CIS28-10S	CIS28 (check)
Sowing time	25 Apr	25 Apr
Days to 50% flowering	15 Jul	25 Jul
Duration (d)	111	121
Plant height (cm)	66	85
Panicle length (cm)	18	17.2
Panicles (no./hill)	14.2	12.1
Grains (no./panicle)	131.5	135.1
1000-grain weight (g)	26	25.8
Exerted stigma (%)	48.3	42.6

The critical stage of sterility transformation is about 15 Jul and fertility transformation 20 Sep under the climatic

conditions of Xiangtan. Under natural conditions, there is no pollen in the anther 15 Jul-20 Sep. We consider sunlight period to be the primary factor affecting its sterility and fertility transformation; air temperature is not important. This means it is a truly photoperiod-sensitive, genic male-sterile rice. ■

Breeding methods— tissue culture

Embryogenic cell suspension and plant regeneration from protoplasts of indica rice

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Cell suspension established from anther-derived callus of indica rice cultivar IR43 was used for protoplast isolation and culture.

Callus was induced following the standard anther culture technique developed at IRRI: Anthers inoculated individually in plastic petri dishes (60 × 15 mm) containing 6 ml of SK-1 medium, and cultures incubated in the dark at 25 ± 1 °C for 1 mo.

Embryogenic calli (approximately 2 g) were selected and placed in 125-ml Erlenmeyer flasks containing 30 ml of liquid AA medium to initiate suspension cultures. The cultures were placed on a gyrotary shaker (120 rpm) in the dark at 25 ± 1 °C. Liquid medium was replaced every 5-6 d. After 3-4 mo, the actively dividing embryogenic cell suspension established was maintained by weekly subculturing at 1:4 dilution (suspension inoculum: fresh medium).

To isolate protoplasts, 3- to 4-d-old cells were incubated for 4 h in a solution containing 1.0% Cellulase Onozuka RS, 0.2% Pectolyase Y-23,5 mM MES, CPW salts, and 13% mannitol at pH 5.6. The protoplasts were sieved through 45- to 25-µm nylon mesh, collected by centrifuging at 100 × g for 5 min, and washed 3 times in CPW salts containing 13% mannitol.

Protoplasts were cultured in 60- × 15-mm plastic petri dishes containing 3 ml MS1 medium at 1-2 × 10⁵ pp/ml, and maintained in the dark at 25 ± 1 °C. After 3-4 wk, the agarose layer was cut into four blocks and transferred to a fresh medium without glucose but supplemented with 3.0% sucrose.

For plant regeneration, 100 calli about 4-5 mm in diameter were transferred to test tubes containing 20 ml of MSYo medium and kept under 12 h darknight photoperiod at 25 ± 1 °C.

Media compositions (SK-1, AA, MS1, MSYo) and growth substances used for different steps of the cultures are given in the table.

Media composition.

Constituent	Amount (mg/liter)			
	SK-1	AA	MS1	MSYo
KNO ₃	3,150	-	1,900	1,900
NH ₄ NO ₃	-	-	1,650	1,650
KH ₂ PO ₄	540	170	170	170
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	150	440	440	440
MGSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	185	370	370	370
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	27.85	27.85	27.85	27.85
Na ₂ EDTA	37.25	37.25	37.25	37.25
KCl	-	2,940	0	0
KI	1.0	0.83	0.83	0.83
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	-	0.025	0.025	0.025
Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
CuSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	10	8.6	8.6	8.6
MnSO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	22.3	22.3	22.3	22.3
H ₃ BO ₃	6	6.2	6.2	6.2
Inositol	100	100	100	100
Nicotinic acid	2.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Pyridoxine-HCl	2.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Thiamine-HCl	2.5	0.1	0.1	0.1
Glycine	2.0	75.0	2.0	2.0
L-glutamine	-	877	-	-
L-aspartic acid	-	266	-	-
L-arginine	-	228	-	-
Sucrose	40,000	30,000	-	30,000
Glucose	-	-	90,000	-
Casein hydrolysate	500	-	-	-
2,4-D	0.75	2.0	1.0	-
NAA	2.5	-	-	1.0
Kinetin	0.75	0.2	-	1.0
GA ₃	-	0.1	-	-
Agar	8,000	-	-	8,000
Agarose	-	-	5,000	-
PH	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.8

The type of callus used (see figure, 1) was highly suitable for developing a suspension culture composed of small groups of cytoplasmic and starch-containing embryogenic cells (2). Protoplasts isolated from this suspension displayed dense cytoplasm (3).

The first division was observed after 4 d of culture (4); multicellular structures were formed after 8-10 d of culture (5). Within 3 wk of culture, most of the structure underwent further growth leading to the direct formation of recognizable globular embryoids (6). Colony formation was counted at this stage. About 0.5-0.75% plated protoplasts formed colonies. Upon transfer to